

Interview Protocols

Material Passport for Reused Composite Materials.

Master's Thesis, ITE504. Fateme Rezaei, Mälardalen University, 2026.

Overview

This appendix contains the question protocols used in the seven semi structured interviews conducted for this thesis. Four interviews were carried out for data collection and three interviews for validation of the prototype. All participants are identified by role only. Recording consent was confirmed at the start of every session, and quotations in the body of the thesis are attributed by role.

Coding and categorisation of the interview material were conducted in Excel for all interview sessions. However the coded material and related worksheets are not included in this appendix due to confidentiality agreements and ethical restrictions.

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SECTION A

Data collection interviews

The following four protocols were used in the data collection phase of the study. The objective at this stage was to surface the information needs of stakeholders along the wind turbine blade reuse value chain, the documentation practices already in place, and the gaps that a material passport for reused composites would need to address.

Producer

Technical and operational perspective

Topic: current documentation, segment level data, value chain gaps, confidentiality. Mode: in person at the WingBeam factory or online via video conference.

Part 1. Current documentation situation

Q1. Can you walk me through what documentation currently exists for your noise barrier products, what do you have today?

Follow up. Is this documentation stored digitally or on paper? Is it consistent across products?

Q2. When a customer asks for product information, what can you currently provide them, and what do you have to say you do not have yet?

Follow up. How does the customer usually react when information is missing?

Q3. What information do you collect at the decommissioning stage, at the point where the blade is cut into segments?

Follow up. Is this documented per segment, or only at the blade level?

Part 2. Segment level material data

Q1. Which segments of a wind turbine blade do you use for noise barriers specifically? How do you identify and select these segments?

Follow up. What are the key differences between segments used for noise barriers and those used for sleepers?

Q2. For each blade segment, what material properties do you currently know? For example: fibre orientation, layer structure, mechanical strength?

Follow up. Do you receive this data from the blade manufacturer, or do you test it yourselves?

Q3. If you had detailed material data for each blade segment, such as composition, strength, and fibre configuration, how would that change your ability to qualify and sell your products?

Follow up. Would it make customer approval faster or easier?

Part 3. Traceability and data flow

Q1. Can you currently trace a finished noise barrier back to the specific blade and segment it came from?

Follow up. Is this information recorded anywhere in your system?

Q2. What happens to the blade's original documentation when it arrives at your facility? Do you receive any technical data sheets or material certificates from the blade producer?

Follow up. If yes, what format are they in? If no, why not?

Part 4. Confidentiality

Q1. Have blade manufacturers or OEMs ever refused to share detailed material data with you because they consider it commercially sensitive?

Follow up. What types of data are they most protective about?

Q2. In your view, what data should be visible to the final customer, and what should remain confidential between you and the blade supplier?

Follow up. How do you balance transparency with protecting proprietary information?

Part 5. Ideal material passport

Q1. If you could design a material passport system for your products, what would it contain? What would it look like?

Follow up. Should it be a physical document, a digital file, a QR code, or something else?

Q2. This research aims to create a generalisable framework that other companies reusing composite materials could adapt. What advice would you give to make the passport useful beyond just WingBeam?

Construction engineer and technical buyer

Public infrastructure and noise barrier projects

Topic: technical specifications needed, product approval process, qualification requirements. Mode: online via video conference.

Part 1. Product approval process

Q1. When you are considering a new construction material for a project, what is your process for evaluating and approving it?

Follow up. Who else is involved in this decision?

Q2. What technical documentation do you typically require before you can specify a product, for example for noise barriers?

Follow up. Are there standard formats or certifications you look for?

Q3. Have you ever rejected or delayed a product because the documentation was insufficient? What was missing?

Part 2. Material information needs

Q1. If you received a noise barrier made from recycled wind turbine blade material, what material information would you need to feel confident using it?

Follow up. Would knowing the exact origin and composition of the material matter to you?

Q2. How important is traceability to you, knowing exactly which blade, from which wind farm, was used to make the product?

Follow up. Is this a regulatory requirement or more of a personal or professional preference?

Q3. What level of detail do you need about the composite material itself? For example: fibre type, resin system, layer structure, mechanical properties?

Follow up. Would segment level data, the properties of specific blade sections, be valuable?

Part 3. Sustainability and environmental data

Q1. Do your projects have sustainability or CO2 requirements? How do you document the environmental performance of materials?

Follow up. Are Environmental Product Declarations or LCA documents something you work with?

Q2. What would a material passport need to contain for you to consider it complete and trustworthy?

Procurement officer

Public sector construction procurement

Topic: purchasing decisions, sustainability criteria, green procurement, documentation requirements. Mode: online via video conference.

Part 1. Procurement process

Q1. How does sustainability factor into your procurement decisions for construction materials?

Follow up. Is there a percentage weighting for environmental criteria in your tender evaluations?

Q2. What kind of documentation do suppliers typically provide, and what do you wish they provided that they currently do not?

Q3. If a product is made from recycled or reused material, does that make it more or less attractive to you, and why?

Part 2. Material passports and traceability

Q1. Are you familiar with the concept of a material passport? Have you ever worked with one?

Follow up. If yes, what format was it in? Was it useful?

Q2. What information in a material passport would most directly support your purchasing decision?

Follow up. For example: CO2 data, test certificates, origin traceability, compliance documentation?

Q3. How do you currently verify that a supplier's environmental claims are accurate?

Follow up. Would a standardised passport help, or would you still need third party verification?

Q4. Would knowing that a product is made from reused composite materials rather than virgin materials give it an advantage in procurement evaluation?

Follow up. How much weight would that carry?

R&D and production manager

WingBeam

Topic: material variability, product design, testing and qualification, ideal documentation system. Mode: in person at the WingBeam facility.

Section A. R and D and product development

Part 1. Blade material properties and product design

Q1. When you receive decommissioned blades, how do you decide which sections to use for which products: beams, noise barriers, or sleepers?

Follow up. What physical characteristics do you look for? How much does blade position, root or tip, matter?

Q2. What are the critical material properties that each product type requires? How do requirements differ between beams, noise barriers, and sleepers?

Follow up. For noise barriers specifically, what properties matter most?

Q3. When designing a new product, what information about the blade material do you absolutely need to know upfront?

Follow up. Composition data? Mechanical properties? Manufacturing history? Something else?

Q4. In your experience, are there performance differences between products made from different blade sections, even if they look similar?

Follow up. Have you had surprises where material behaved differently than expected?

Part 2. Testing and qualification

Q1. Walk me through your testing process. What do you test before a product can be sold?

Follow up. Are you testing individual segments or finished products? How do you document results?

Q2. When qualifying a product for construction use, what challenges do you face related to material documentation?

Follow up. Do you need to prove material origin? What do customers or certification bodies ask for?

Q3. What documentation do you need to provide when you sell a noise barrier or beam to a customer?

Follow up. Technical specifications? Test certificates? Environmental data, such as EPDs or carbon footprint? Material composition?

Section B. Information gaps and documentation needs

Part 3. Current state and missing information

Q1. When you start working with a new batch of blades, what is the first information you look for?

Follow up. Where do you get this information currently? How reliable is it? What is missing?

Q2. Are there situations where lack of information about the original blade creates problems for your R and D or production?

Follow up. Can you give a specific example? How do you work around missing data?

Q3. Do OEMs such as Vestas or Siemens provide any technical data when blades are decommissioned?

Follow up. If yes, what do they provide? If no, what would you want from them if they were willing?

Q4. From a production efficiency standpoint, what information would save you the most time or reduce costs?

Follow up. Would it reduce testing? Speed up development? Reduce waste?

Section C. Material passport concept

Part 4. Ideal documentation system

Q1. If you could design the perfect information system for tracking blade materials, what would it include?

Follow up. What level of detail, whole blade or segment level? What specific data points? How to access it?

Q2. What would be the top three pieces of information you would want in a material passport for your R and D work?

Q3. If every blade segment had a material passport with technical data, how would that change your R and D or production work?

Follow up. Would it change processes? Enable new products? Reduce costs or risks?

Q4. From a practical standpoint, how would you want to access passport information?

Follow up. Physical document? Digital file such as PDF or Excel? Online database? QR code?

Q5. Would segment level traceability, tracking individual blade sections, be useful for your work?

Follow up. Why or why not? At what granularity level? What would you do with that detail?

Section D. Challenges and future vision

Part 5. Barriers and opportunities

Q1. From your R and D perspective, what is the biggest challenge in scaling up production of blade based products?

Follow up. Material supply? Technical variability? Market acceptance? Regulatory or certification matters?

Q2. Looking five to ten years ahead, what would make reused blade materials as easy to work with as traditional construction materials?

Follow up. Standardisation? Better documentation? Regulatory recognition? Something else?

SECTION B

Validation interviews

The following three protocols were used to validate the prototype material passport. Two participants from the data collection phase reviewed how their earlier input had been translated into the design, and a third, independent participant from a customer side organisation reviewed the prototype for the first time.

Sales and business development, noise barrier manufacturer

Independent customer side reviewer, Sweden

Validation type: independent, first time seeing the prototype. Duration: about 60 minutes. Mode: online via video conference. The interview was preceded by a pre interview questionnaire sent two days in advance and the prototype document sent one day before the live session.

The protocol for this interview is in two parts. Part one is a pre interview questionnaire sent in advance to capture background on the participant's role, company, and documentation workflow. Part two is the live session, which begins with brief follow ups on the pre questionnaire answers and then focuses on a walk through of the prototype.

Pre interview questionnaire

Sent two days in advance

A. Your role and your company

Q1. In one or two sentences, how would you describe what you do day to day in your role?

Q2. Who are your typical customers? Public infrastructure such as road or rail authorities, private contractors, or both? If you can give a rough split, for example seventy percent public and thirty percent private, that is helpful.

Q3. When your customers evaluate a noise barrier product for purchase, what kind of documentation do they typically ask for? Examples: data sheets, EPDs, test certificates, supplier specifications, third party verification, sustainability reports.

B. How documentation works today

Q1. When a new noise barrier product comes in for evaluation, what is the first thing you look at? What do you need to know before you can take it seriously as a procurement option?

Q2. What format does this documentation usually arrive in? PDFs, web pages, supplier portals, paper data sheets, or something else? How is it structured: one document per product, or scattered across multiple sources?

Q3. Is there anything that is painful about documentation in your work today? Anything missing, hard to find, or in the wrong format?

C. Customer expectations

Q1. In Sweden, how does environmental weighting work in public procurement for noise barriers? Is there an equivalent to the Norwegian rule that gives thirty percent weight to environmental criteria?

Q2. What environmental documentation do your customers typically expect? EPDs, third party LCAs, climate declarations, or something else? Practically, would a customer reject a product if the EPD is pending but everything else is in place, or would they accept it conditionally?

Q3. Do your customers ask about due diligence, such as supplier origin, country risk, and human rights compliance, or is environmental performance the main focus?

D. Reused materials in your context

Q1. Has your company worked with reused or recycled materials in noise barriers before? If yes, briefly: what materials, and how was the documentation handled?

Q2. From a documentation point of view, setting aside price and product fit, what would a passport for reused blade products need to include before your customers would accept the product?

Live session

Part 1. Pre questionnaire follow up

Part 1. First impressions of the prototype

Q1. What does this document seem to be for?

Q2. Who do you think made it, what kind of company or organisation?

Q3. Who do you think it is meant for, who is the reader?

Part 2. Section by section walk through

Q1. Section 1, identity and lifecycle. This section shows the product's first life as a wind turbine blade and its second life as a noise barrier. Does this two lifecycle split make sense to you? Do you currently see this kind of documentation in noise barrier supply chains, or is this new?

Q2. Section 6, environmental and EPD. The EPD is marked as pending. If you received this passport with a sales pitch, would your customers accept a pending EPD, or is it a deal breaker until the EPD is complete?

Follow up. Does this section give you what you would need for a Swedish customer? Is there anything in this environmental section that is missing for your kind of customer?

Q3. Section 8, regulatory and standards. Each row uses one of these statuses: designed for, targeted, pending, passed, failed. Does that vocabulary make sense to you? Would your customers' procurement teams accept these statuses, or do they need everything to be passed before they will consider the product?

Q4. Section 10, three component system. The passport comes in three parts: a stainless steel tag riveted to the panel, a digital web record, and a downloadable PDF. Does that match how durable product documentation works in your industry? Is it overkill or insufficient?

Q5. Access tier strip. There are four access tiers: public, procurement, engineer, producer. Which of these tiers would you expect to access in your role? Would tier two, procurement, give you what you need, or would you also want tier three, engineer, information?

Q6. Provenance system. Every value carries one of these symbols: tested, inferred, calculated, OEM only, or missing. Right now most values in this prototype are inferred. If you received a passport where most values are inferred, would that be useful for sales conversations, or would your customers want everything to be tested?

Q7. After each section, two follow ups: is there anything missing in this section that you would need; is there anything here that does not matter to you.

Part 3. Business perspective

Q1. If you imagine sourcing noise barrier panels from this kind of producer in the next twelve to twenty four months, would this passport make that sourcing easier, harder, or about the same as your current process?

Q2. What would this passport need to do that it does not currently do, before your company would treat it as a real procurement document rather than a thesis prototype?

Q3. Are there things your customers ask for in the public infrastructure space, such as environmental claims or due diligence, that are not covered here?

Part 4. Closing

Q1. Looking at the whole document, is anything missing that you would need before you could use this professionally?

Q2. Is anything here that strikes you as wrong, confusing, or unnecessary?

Q3. If you had to give this to a colleague tomorrow and explain it in one sentence, what would you say?

Q4. Consent to quote: I would like to use some of your feedback in my thesis, attributed by role only, not by name. Is that acceptable to you?

Validation follow up, technical perspective

WingBeam, returning participant from the data collection phase

Validation type: follow up with a participant from the data collection phase, now reviewing the prototype. Focus: segment structure, traceability, confidentiality, long term durability of the passport. Mode: online via video conference. The prototype was shared on screen and walked through before the questions.

Reflection on the prototype

Q1. In the first interview, you explained that the blade changes a lot from root to tip, with different thicknesses, fibre directions, and materials in different areas. That discussion became the basis for the S1 to S10 segment structure in the passport. Does this way of dividing and documenting the blade make sense from a practical point of view?

Q2. You also explained that some parts of the blade are much more useful structurally than others, especially for railway sleepers and noise barriers. I tried to reflect that by separating the stronger and weaker sections in the traceability structure. Does the prototype communicate that clearly enough?

Q3. You said that a lot of supplier information is still confidential or unavailable, and that sometimes you have to estimate or rely on your own testing. That became one of the reasons for the provenance marking system and the verification labels. Do you think the current system handles uncertainty in an honest and realistic way?

Q4. You mentioned that customers mainly care about mechanical stability, environmental safety, and proof that recycled material is actually being used. I tried to prioritise those areas in the passport structure. Looking at it now, does the prototype focus on the right information from a customer perspective?

Q5. You talked about traceability and said you want to be able to track products back to a specific blade number. That became an important part of the traceability section in the passport. Does the level of traceability in the prototype feel realistic for how your process actually works?

Q6. You explained that some information should stay confidential while some information needs to be visible to customers. That discussion influenced the four tier structure and the different access levels in the prototype. Does that structure make sense to you now that you see it visually?

Q7. You mentioned that a QR code alone would probably not survive for fifty years, and that long term database storage would still be necessary. That became the reason for the three part system: physical tag, digital passport, and archival documentation. Do you think this combination works for long term infrastructure products?

Q8. I also included recycling and second life instructions because you mentioned that customers may eventually need guidance for what happens after the second life of the product. Does this section feel useful, or is there something important missing?

Q9. One thing I am still unsure about is the balance between transparency and readability. For example, some OEM fields are left incomplete because the information is unavailable. From your perspective, is it better to show missing information openly, or would customers prefer a cleaner and simpler document?

Q10. Looking at the prototype as a whole, does it feel realistic as something that could actually support discussions with infrastructure customers, municipalities, or procurement actors?

Q11. Is there anything important from our first interview that you feel is still missing from the passport?

Q12. If a system like this existed in practice, what do you think would be the biggest challenge for implementing it in the industry?

Validation follow up, commercial and procurement perspective

WingBeam, returning participant from the data collection phase

Validation type: follow up with a participant from the data collection phase, now reviewing the prototype. Focus: procurement, environmental weighting, third party verification, due diligence. Mode: online via video conference.

Environmental weighting and procurement

Q1. In our first conversation, you mentioned that public companies in Norway are required to weight environment around thirty percent in procurement. That influenced how I structured this environmental section. EPD status, reused content, and environmental qualification are made very visible in the passport. Does this feel realistic from a procurement perspective?

EPD and third party verification

Q1. You also mentioned that EPD or LCA information should come from somebody other than the company itself. That influenced how I handled verification in the prototype. Instead of presenting everything as fully confirmed, I separated four statuses: passed, targeted, pending, and designed for. Does that distinction make sense from your procurement perspective?

QR code and passport structure

Q1. When we talked about the battery passport, you mentioned that the QR code was a requirement there. That influenced the structure here as well. The passport became a physical tag connected to a digital record, with long term archival backup behind it. Does this structure feel realistic to you?

Due diligence and supplier risk

Q1. One thing that stayed with me from our first conversation was when you talked about supplier risk and due diligence before environmental performance. You mentioned things like supplier country, risk regions, media attention, and human rights concerns. While building the prototype I realised I do not yet include that properly. What kind of due diligence information would procurement actually expect to see in a system like this?

Q2. Would that information normally be self declared, or externally verified?

Circularity and second life logic

Q1. You talked about construction companies being under pressure to reduce CO2 emissions and increase circularity. That influenced the whole first life and second life structure of the passport. The idea

was not only to show where the material came from, but also to preserve the identity of the material across different lifecycles. Does that logic make sense from your perspective?

Realism and industry adoption

Q1. At the end of our first conversation, you mentioned that systems like this are probably still several years away from full adoption. After seeing the prototype now, does it still feel realistic to you? Or does anything feel too ambitious or difficult for industry adoption?

Trust and inferred data

Q1. A lot of the values in the passport are marked as inferred, pending, or estimated from literature. From a procurement perspective, does that transparency increase trust? Or would too much uncertainty make the system harder to use?

Public transparency

Q1. Do you think public facing transparency like this actually matters in infrastructure projects? Or is the passport mainly useful internally for procurement and compliance?

Closing questions

Q1. Looking at the prototype overall, which section feels most valuable or most useful from your perspective?

Q2. If you received something like this from a supplier tomorrow, what would be the first thing you would look at?

Q3. Is there anything important missing that you expected to see here?